

2. *Treatment of the ether layer (G).*—The oily residue (0.005 g.) obtained after the removal of ether had an indole-like faecal odour, and responded to the tests of an indole (pine chip reaction). Neither the residue nor its derivatives could be obtained in a solid state to facilitate further examinations.

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COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH BIVALENT METALS. PART IV. PALLADIUM BIGUANIDINE AND ITS SALTS

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Palladium is known to resemble nickel in many of its chemical properties and possesses like the latter an electronic structure of the pseudo-inert gas type. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study the preparation and properties of palladium biguanide complexes and compare them with those of nickel. Besides palladium biguanidine and its hydroxide, a number of other salts, namely, chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, thiosulphate, thiocyanate, nitrate, palladothiocyanate, chloropalladite and chloroplatinate have been described in this paper. The palladium biguanide complex resembles the corresponding nickel complex, but is more stable and comparatively less soluble. The complex thiocyanate undergoes an interesting disproportionation in presence of acid to form palladium biguanidinium palladothiocyanate.

In parts I and II of this series, copper and nickel biguanidines and their salts have been described (Rây and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 617; Rây and Purakayastha, *ibid.*, 1941, 18, 217). As nickel and palladium resemble each other in many of their chemical properties and possess an electronic structure of pseudo-inert gas type, it was naturally expected that complex palladium biguanide compounds, similar to those of nickel, could be readily obtained. The present paper deals with the preparation and properties of these compounds. Besides palladium biguanidine and its hydroxides, a number of palladium biguanidinium salts, *viz.*, chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, thiosulphate, nitrate, thiocyanate, palladothiocyanate, chloropalladite and chloroplatinate, have been prepared. Their solubility and other properties follow the corresponding nickel compounds, but are somewhat more intensified regarding their complex character. In other words, the palladium complexes are relatively more stable and less soluble than their nickel analogues. The palladium biguanide complex is light yellow in colour and diamagnetic. Hence, like the corresponding nickel complex it is believed to possess a planar configuration with dsp^2 hybrid bonds.

The light yellow palladium biguanidinium thiocyanate in presence of a little acid suffers an interesting disproportionation giving rise to palladium biguanidinium palladothiocyanate (reddish brown) with partial elimination of biguanide.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Palladium bisBiguanidinium Hydroxide.—Fine, silky, light yellow crystals of the complex base were precipitated by the addition of palladous chloride solution to that of biguanide sulphate in an excess of alkali. It was washed first by decantation with cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air free from CO_2 . {Found: N, 41.51; Pd, 31.42. $[\text{Pd}(\text{BigH}^+)_2](\text{OH})_2$ requires N, 40.85; Pd, 31.13 per cent}. Magnetic susceptibility, $\chi_m = 0.259 \times 10^{-6}$.

Palladium bisBiguanidine.—When the above hydroxide was heated to 115° it lost 10.52% of its weight and changed into anhydro base. {Found: Pd, 34.72. $[\text{Pd}(\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_6)_2]$ requires Pd, 34.78 per cent}.

Palladium bisBiguanidinium Chloride.—A light yellow solution of the chloride was obtained by neutralising the complex hydroxide, suspended in water, with 2*N*-HCl. On cooling, the light yellow crystals of the chloride separated out. These were washed first with a little ice-cold water, then with alcohol and finally dried in air. The substance can also be obtained by the action of ammonium chloride on the complex base. {Found: Cl, 17.11; Pd, 25.55. $[\text{Pd}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 17.06; Pd, 25.67 per cent}.

Equivalent conductivity at 28° .

v (litres)	...	64	128	256	512	1024
λ_p	...	103.68	108.80	111.30	113.45	113.88

λ_∞ (mean) = 120.76 from Walden's formula.

The mobility of $1/2 [\text{Pd}(\text{BigH}^+)_2] = 120.76 - 79.33 - 41.43$, the mobility of chlorine ion at 28° being 79.33. The value for the corresponding Ni-complex ion at 25° (Rây and Purakayastha, *loc. cit.*) is equal to 46.27. On making necessary correction for the temperature difference it will be found that the mobility of the complex palladium biguanide ion is considerably lower than that of its nickel analogue. This is in agreement with their respective atomic radius. The values of their atomic radii, according to Goldschidt, are Ni = 1.244×10^{-8} cm. and Pd = 1.370×10^{-8} cm. respectively.

The bromide was prepared by adding a strong solution of potassium bromide to that of the complex chloride. It forms light yellow crystals moderately soluble in water. {Found: Br, 33.02; Pd, 21.80. $[\text{Pd}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{Br}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Br, 32.86; Pd, 21.94 per cent}.

The iodide was prepared in the same way as the bromide using potassium iodide. Recrystallised from water it forms light yellow crystals, moderately soluble in water, but freely soluble in alcohol. The colour of the substance changes gradually to light

brown, possibly with slight decomposition. {Found: N, 23.55; I, 42.45; Pd, 17.95; H₂O (by loss at 105°), 6.03. [Pd (BigH⁺)₂]I₂. 2H₂O requires N, 23.39; I, 42.41; Pd, 17.82; H₂O, 6.3 per cent}.

Sulphate.—Yellowish white, curdy precipitate of the sulphate was obtained by adding a solution of potassium sulphate to that of the complex chloride. The substance is almost insoluble in water. {Found: N, 30.98; Pd, 23.02; SO₄, 20.79. [Pd (BigH⁺)₂] SO₄.3H₂O requires N, 30.53; Pd, 23.26; SO₄, 20.92 per cent}.

Thiosulphate.—Practically insoluble, curdy, light buff-coloured precipitate of the thiosulphate was obtained by adding a solution of sodium thiosulphate to that of the complex chloride. The substance is not acted upon by dilute alkalis. {Found: S, 13.62; Pd, 22.55. [Pd (BigH⁺)₂] S₂O₃.3H₂O requires S, 13.49; Pd, 22.49 per cent}.

The nitrate was obtained as a yellowish white, crystalline precipitate when a solution of potassium nitrate was added to that of the complex chloride. It was purified by recrystallisation from hot water. {Found: Pd, 24.58; NO₃, 28.23. [Pd (BigH⁺)₂](NO₃)₂ requires Pd, 24.65; NO₃, 28.65 per cent}.

Thiocyanate.—When a strong solution of potassium thiocyanate was added to that of the complex chloride, very light yellow, silky needles of the complex thiocyanate separated out. This was recrystallised from water, washed with ice-cold water and dried in air. The substance is highly soluble in alcohol. In presence of a little acid it changes into a light brown, insoluble product described below. {Found S, 14.50; Pd, 24.05. [Pd (BigH⁺)₂](SCN)₂.H₂O requires S, 14.45; Pd, 24.10 per cent}.

Palladothiocyanate.—As stated above it results from the action of dilute acids upon the previous compound. It was also prepared by the addition of a solution of potassium palladothiocyanate to that of the complex chloride. The substance forms red-brown, silky crystals, insoluble in water. {Found: N, 30.52; S, 19.54, 19.70; Pd, 33.06, 33.04. [Pd (BigH⁺)₂] Pd (SCN)₄ requires N, 30.27; S, 19.77; Pd, 32.96 per cent}.

Chloropalladite.—When a solution of potassium palladochloride was added to that of the complex chloride, the light yellow crystals, changing to brownish yellow, of the complex chloropalladite separated out. These were washed with ice-cold water and dried over conc. H₂SO₄. It dissolves in hot water with decomposition. It is soluble in alcohol. {Found: Cl, 25.30; Pd, 38.31. [Pd (BigH⁺)₂] PdCl₄ requires Cl, 25.45; Pd, 38.38 per cent}.

The chloroplatinate was obtained as a bright yellow, insoluble precipitate by adding a solution of sodium chloroplatinate to that of the complex chloride. {Found: Cl, 26.46; Pd, 13.25; Pt, 24.12. [Pd (Big H⁺)₂] PtCl₆.5H₂O requires, Cl, 26.37; Pd, 13.22; Pt, 24.19 per cent}.

The palladium biguanide complex also forms interesting polyhalides, which will be described in a separate paper.

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